

Assesment of a UAV positioning system based on MLAT techniques to a 5G network for Urban Air Mobility

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Abstract- This paper aims to test the feasibility of using the 5G mobile network to obtain the position of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) based on multilateration (MLAT) positioning systems. The strategy employed is to test whether the topology of a cellular network deployed in a coverage area meets the positioning accuracy requirements for aircraft. In this case, an Urban Air Mobility (UAM) use case has been considered in Valencia, where it has been assumed that aircraft will follow a particular flight path between two vertiports. In addition, an optimization technique based on genetic algorithms has also been employed to select the optimal spatial distribution of already deployed base stations that provide the best levels of accuracy and thus minimize the resources employed.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the unmanned aircraft industry has attracted interest due to its potential and many applications. The aircraft positioning systems proposed to date [1],[2] are based on ADS (Automatic Dependent Surveillance) surveillance, which integrates a GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) receiver. However, in urban environments, using GNSS signals to obtain the drone's position can be complex due to the masking effect of satellites by buildings and multipath. In addition, using a single source of information can compromise safety in critical applications. Therefore, in the last few years, solutions have been proposed to estimate the position of aircraft from other signals, such as mobile networks.

This work aims to test the feasibility of using the 5G cell phone network to obtain the target's position by using hyperbolic positioning or multilateration (MLAT). Furthermore, metaheuristic optimization techniques will be applied to find the best spatial distribution of the base stations deployed in the coverage area. This work has been applied to an Urban Air Mobility (UAM) case.

In the following, Section II presents the MLAT system and Cramér Rao Lower Bound (CRLB) analysis method to obtain the system's accuracy. Section III tackle positioning using mobile networks, and Section IV explains the entire process implemented and the results obtained. Finally, Section V contains the main conclusions.

II. MLAT AND CRAMÉR RAO LOWER BOUND

A multilateration (MLAT) system, known as a hyperbolic positioning system, is an Air Traffic Control (ATC) surveillance method. The system typically uses Mode S and Mode A/C replies to secondary radar interrogation to locate and identify aircraft and vehicles equipped with transponders.

To perform these functions, at least three stations are required for two-dimensional (2D) or four for three-dimensional (3D) surveillance, with the capability to measure specific characteristics, such as Time of Arrival (TOA), Round Trip Delay (RTD) and Angle of Arrival (AOA).

The system generally consists of some receiver/interrogator stations deployed in a particular coverage area and a central computer running a set of algorithms to calculate the target's position. The stations send the measured information to a Central Processing Subsystem (CPS), which will perform the transponder positioning calculations. Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the localization system

The accuracy of position estimation in MLAT systems depends on the position of the stations and the system's geometry, related to a factor called Dilution of Precision (DOP). This factor depends on the target's position and the MLAT stations' positions that contribute to the target's location. The main design objective is to deploy the minimum number of stations to obtain the requested system coverage while complying with all regulatory standards and constraints imposed by each particular site.

As previously mentioned, MLAT systems collect specific measurements from a set of receiving stations and then obtain a target position by solving hyperbolic equations. In this case, the process implemented is based on [3] and consists of characterizing the error that the Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA) measurement would present to obtain the accuracy of the coverage area.

The objective of the positioning system is to know the target's position at a given time from the stations' measurements. However, due to the TOA measurement error, the multilateration system does not provide the target position but only an estimate of it. Assuming that the TOA measurement error has zero mean, the estimator is unbiased. Since the estimator is unbiased, there is a lower bound of the TOA measurement error, the Cramér Rao Lower Bound (CRLB). This bound is considered the system's Theoretical Expected Precision (PTE). In general, the CRLB provides Root Mean Square (RMS) error bounds or standard deviation of the error in each direction of space ($\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$), which can be combined to define different quality parameters of the system.

In addition, the hybrid technique consisting of TDOA and AOA measurement can be also implemented. In this way, the aim is to improve the system by adding to the stations the capacity to measure the vertical AOA of the signal emitted by the transponder. For this purpose, the process carried out in [4] can be followed, where the error in the measurement of the TDOA and AOA are combined to obtain the system's accuracy as a whole and to take advantage of the benefits of both technologies which provide a significant improvement in accuracy.

III. POSITIONING VIA MOBILE NETWORKS

The Radio Access Technology (RAT) dependent positioning methods detailed in 3GPP, are classified according to the type of positioning measurement they use, namely timing, signal power, and angle, in addition to possible hybrid positioning techniques.

This work uses the Uplink Time Difference of Arrival (UL-TDOA) and Uplink Angle of Arrival (UL-AOA) method, standardized in release 16 for 5G NR. It consists of each station (gNB) measuring the timing and the angle of arrival of the uplink Sounding Reference Signal (SRS) of the mobile device and providing this information to the Location Management Function (LMF) of the 5G NR network. This SRS is a significant difference from previous generations and is used by stations for uplink channel polling, including channel estimation and synchronization.

The NG-RAN positioning architecture is depicted in Fig. 2. The control channels share location data between UE, network nodes, and positioning servers in control plane-based system that 3GPP has defined. In NR, the position data is exchanged using two different methods. Signaling between the user equipment (UE), the Location Management Function (LMF), and the location server, such as the Evolved Serving Mobile Location Center (E-SMLC), is covered by the LPP (LTE Positioning Protocol). Procedures for exchanging positioning-related data between NG-RAN nodes and LMF are defined in the NRPPa (NR Positioning Protocol Annex). The network base stations in NG-RAN, known as gNB (Next Generation Node B) and ng-eNB (Next Generation Enhance Node B), are responsible for handling communication between NG-RAN and LMF in CN (Core Network), performing uplink positioning measurements, and receiving positioning queries from LMF.

Fig. 2. NG-RAN positioning architecture

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Methodology

This work has been applied to an UAM case in an urban scenario, in which the 5G base stations are intended to receive the signals transmitted by the onboard transponder in the aircraft and, from them, measure its positioning accuracy using the multilateration techniques.

Firstly, a coverage area has been selected in the city of Valencia in which two vertiports have been defined, connected by a corridor through which the aircraft will circulate. This corridor has been assigned a longitude of 4.96 km and an amplitude size of 500 meters for its analysis. Next, all the mobile telephone base stations of the same operator (Orange) have been selected, aiming to check whether only one can provide this service. Fig. 3 shows the coverage area and differentiates the BS (Base Stations) that offer 5G services by the green markings and those that still offer 4G services in blue (this information is public [5],[6]). However, for the study, all of them have been considered as 5G stations. The coverage area is 3.76 km x 6.12 km, where 42 base stations are available for the study.

Once the coverage area and base stations have been obtained, the positioning techniques and optimization process explained below will be implemented.

Fig. 3. Coverage area and BS

B. Optimization process

The aim of this work is to assess whether 5G mobile phone base stations already deployed in a certain coverage area could be used for UAV positioning using multilateration techniques. That is why it has been decided to use an optimisation process. Its objective is to find the best way to use the available resources in such a way that all the requirements and constraints are met. In this way, the aim is to select the best spatial distribution of the stations, with the minimum number of stations possible, that meet the requirements imposed.

The method used consists of Genetic Algorithms (GA), which are metaheuristic optimization methods inspired by nature, which belong to the Evolutionary Computation (EC) family, and solve constrained and unconstrained optimization problems based on the process that drives biological evolution.

The aim is to find the combination of stations that will provide us with the best levels of accuracy in the selected coverage area. Therefore, it must be understood that an individual (in GA) will consist of a set of stations and that different individuals, i.e., different combinations of stations, will form a population. Thus, the fitness function will analyze all station combinations in the population. Once evaluated, individuals (sets of stations) will be selected to form the next generation. Using the crossover and mutation operators, new individuals (new sets of stations) will be formed, repeating the process until the stop conditions are met.

C. Design process

The general design procedure that has been developed is oriented toward designing MLAT systems with receiving 5G base stations capable of measuring the TOA/TDOA of a signal sent by a transponder. In this case, the transponder onboard the aircraft will transmit a broadcast signal so the base stations can detect it (it has been assumed that the aircraft has an isotropic antenna). As for the 5G positioning techniques, UL-TDOA and UL-TDOA+UL-AoA are used.

In this sense, the system design is obtained by calculating the minimum number of stations and their positions in order to maximize the Line of Sight (LoS) coverage and the theoretical accuracy of the system. Thus, Fig. 4 shows the optimization algorithm as an iterative procedure in which specific inputs such as coverage area, station locations, requirements, and constraints (e.g., the minimum separation between stations or required accuracy levels) are introduced. Secondly, a random set of stations, the initial population, is selected, and then the numerical tools are applied. Among the necessary numerical tools are those for calculating the LoS, errors, and theoretical accuracy of the system. Once these calculations have been made, the values are entered into the fitness function to evaluate the quality of the design, i.e., the spatial distribution of the stations, and thus, obtain a score about the requirements and restrictions. Finally, it is checked whether the stopping condition is fulfilled, i.e., the requirements and constraints or a maximum number of iterations are met. If so, the solution to the problem (the number of stations and their location) is obtained. If not, the implemented genetic algorithm iteratively modifies this partial solution until the stop condition is reached.

D. Results

As for the results, these have been obtained for a frequency of 4 GHz (FR1 (Frequency Range 1) of 5G NR) and the maximum available bandwidth, 100 MHz. In addition, it is assumed that the base stations are perfectly synchronized, that they are at a height between 20 and 50 meters to assume the height of the buildings (randomly selected), and that the antennas have a gain of 0 dB. Regarding the aircraft, it has been assumed to fly at 120 m above ground level, and its antenna has a gain of 0 dBi with a power of 57 dBm.

Positioning accuracy future requirements for 5G networks were defined in [7]. However, these are more objectives for future UAM applications than requirements. In this work, the

Fig. 4. Diagram of the MLAT design and optimization process

accuracy in the fitness function was 5 meters and 10 meters for horizontal and vertical accuracy, respectively. Regarding the simulation, it has been performed in Matlab.

Fig. 5 shows the results obtained for horizontal accuracy, and Fig. 6 shows the results for vertical accuracy. On the flight path (corridor), an average horizontal accuracy of 2.98 m and a vertical accuracy of 22.71 m has been obtained. In this case, the imposed horizontal accuracy requirements are achieved with 2 meters of margin. However, the vertical accuracy values are more than 10 meters from the imposed requirement.

Concerning the genetic algorithm, the lowest value obtained, i.e., the best, was 0.326081. This value was achieved using a total of 24 stations. Fig. 7 shows how a total of 296 stations can be seen and how 296 generations have been carried out before reaching the stopping criterion, with a maximum of $3.5369 \cdot 10^{11}$ possible combinations. In this case, the algorithm stops if no better value than the last one obtained is reached after 100 generations.

Fig. 5. Horizontal accuracy with TDOA

Fig. 6. Vertical accuracy with TDOA

Fig. 7. GA convergence with TDOA

As mentioned above, the hybrid technique consisting of TDOA and AOA measurement is also used. In this way, the aim is to improve the system by adding to the stations a vertical uniform linear array with the capability of measuring the vertical AOA to measure the angle of arrival of the signal emitted by the transponder. Fig. 8, 9 and 10 show the results obtained. The same number of stations has been used as in the previous case, 24, in order to compare the results obtained. Table I summarises the values obtained. It can be seen how a very significant improvement has been obtained by implementing the AOA measurement, especially in the vertical accuracy, where it has been improved by more than 20 m. As for the horizontal accuracy, a slight improvement in its values can be noted.

Fig. 8. Horizontal accuracy with TDOA+AOA

Fig. 9. Vertical accuracy with TDOA+AOA

Fig. 10. GA convergence with TDOA+AOA

TABLE I
Average accuracy obtained

	TDOA	TDOA+AOA
Horizontal	2.98	2.432
Vertical	22.71	0.3473

These results show that the accuracy requirements are not met by using the TDOA measurement alone, but it improves significantly when a hybrid system is implemented. By combining the timing and angle-based methods, the characteristics of both technologies are exploited, providing a significant improvement in accuracy levels.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes an efficient procedure for the layout of MLAT systems. This procedure is based on using GAs together with tools such as CRLB analysis. Using CRLB allows us to compare the performance of different algorithms based on time, angles, and combinations of these. The genetic algorithms have allowed us to find optimal solutions that meet the problem's constraints and requirements, avoiding evaluating all possibilities and thus reducing the computational time. Finally, it has been possible to verify the approximate accuracy levels obtained in an urban environment using 5G technology.

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